

Newsletter 04/2019

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Dissemination and Upcoming Events: Meet Us!

ESIWACE will participate in

- EGU General Assembly, 7-12 April, Vienna/Austria, <https://www.egu2019.eu>
Meet us in the sessions on [Machine Learning for Earth System modelling](#) and [High resolution weather and climate models on large supercomputers](#)!
- Several events in conjunction with the EuroHPC Summit Week, Poznan/Poland: HPC Ecosystem Summit, 15 May; EXDCI-2 Workshop on High Performance Data Analytics, 16 May; General Assembly of the CoEs, 17 May; <https://events.prace-ri.eu/event/850/overview>
- EC-Earth Meeting, 21-23 May, Reading/UK
- Teratec Forum, 11-12 June, Palaiseau/France, http://www.teratec.eu/gb/forum/Cafe_Europeen_Research.html
- Several minisymposia at the Platform for Advanced Scientific Computing (PASC), 12-14 June, Zurich/Switzerland, <https://pasc19.pasc-conference.org>
- ISC HPC, 17-19 June, Frankfurt/Germany, www.isc-hpc.com
ESIWACE will be represented at the booth of DKRZ and in the Project Poster Track!
There will further be a presentation by Peter Bauer, ECMWF: "Exascale Systems Present a Vision for Weather and Climate Prediction – Can we Meet the Challenge?"
- [2nd DYAMOND-ESIWACE Hackathon](#), 18-21 June, Mainz/Germany, <https://www.esiwace.eu/events/19-21-june-2019-diamond-2nd-hackathon-mainz-de>
- 5th OpenIFS workshop, 17-21 June, Reading/UK, <https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/OIFS/5th+OpenIFS+workshop+2019>

- Workshop on Machine Learning for Weather and Climate Models, 2-5 Sep, Oxford/UK, <http://users.ox.ac.uk/~phys0895/mlwc2019/index.html>
- International Computing for Atmospheric Sciences Symposium (iCAS), 8-12 Sep, Stresa/Italy, <https://www2.cisl.ucar.edu/events/conferences/icas/2019>

An Update on the Demonstrators

The work on the global atmosphere-only kilometre-scale demonstrators in IFS and ICON has fed into publications which discuss opportunities and HPC limitations of the high-resolution science case:

- [Schulthess, Bauer, Wedi, Fuhrer, Hoefler and Schär. Reflecting on the Goal and Baseline for Exascale Computing: A Roadmap Based on Weather and Climate Simulations. Computing in Science & Engineering, 2019](#)
- [Neumann, Dueben, Adamidis, Bauer, Brueck, Kornblueh, Klocke, Stevens, Wedi, Biercamp. Assessing the scales in numerical weather and climate predictions: will exascale be the rescue, Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A, 2019](#)
- [P. Bauer. Where are the present computational limits of global high-resolution modelling? 2019](#)

ESiWACE further focused on the ocean-only NEMO demonstrator and on the coupled ocean-atmosphere demonstrators based on ICON and EC-Earth.

Concerning NEMO, 24 000 Broadwell cores were used to measure the performance of a simplified kilometre-scale setup. Assuming perfect scalability on up to 9 000 000 cores, it was inferred that a throughput of 2 SYPD could theoretically be achieved, although at a prohibitive energy cost, based on extrapolation of current architecture energy consumption.

The coupled ocean-atmosphere demonstrators based on EC-Earth and ICON were presented at a workshop on the demonstrators, organised as part of the [ESiWACE General Assembly](#) and ESiWACE2 Kick-Off. EC-EARTH was successfully launched in a 10km-coupled mode, achieving a throughput of 0.44 SYPD with 5 040 MPI tasks on MareNostrum4. For ICON, a 5km-coupled model was established, running at 0.04 SYPD on 3780 MPI tasks (each task running with 4 OpenMP threads).

Find out more about these demonstrators on Zenodo:

- Nemo demonstrator: <https://zenodo.org/record/2596983#.XKSvbaSxU2w>
- EC-Earth coupled demonstrator: <https://zenodo.org/record/2590661#.XKSvwaSxU2w>
- ICON coupled demonstrator: <https://zenodo.org/record/2596977#.XKSvl6SxU2w>

Figure 1. Visualisation of cloud water and ocean circulation after four days of running the 5km-coupled ICON simulation

ESiWACE Review

In November 2018, ESiWACE was reviewed by the European Commission and experts in the field. The project was evaluated positively and has now proceeded into its final project phase which will end on 31 Aug 2019. We thank the reviewers for their feedback and the discussions!

ESiWACE General Assembly and ESIWACE2 Kick-Off

From 11-13 March 2019, members of the Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe met under the umbrella of the General Assembly of ESIWACE, phase 1, and a kick-off meeting for ESIWACE, phase 2.

Besides a review of activities and achievements in all work packages, the ESIWACE General Assembly particularly focused on the established high-resolution demonstrators in IFS, ICON, EC-Earth and NEMO, as well as on the scientific-technical dimensions and future development and sustainability plans.

Some aspects on the latter have already been formulated in terms of strategies for several ESIWACE developments¹, and the newly funded ESIWACE2 will help at achieving short-term sustainability. Yet, the HPC landscape is rapidly changing in terms of hardware development, European infrastructure and strategies; this particularly includes the newly launched EuroHPC Joint Undertaking, related pre- and exascale roadmaps of the European Commission, and an inherent involvement of the centres of excellence—such as ESIWACE—in these developments.

A major goal of ESIWACE2 is to push the demonstrator developments from ESIWACE, phase 1, towards production-ready simulation setups on the upcoming EuroHPC pre-exascale systems. The project will further provide enhanced services and trainings to the community and focus on new technology developments. Intense exchange was sought during the ESIWACE2 kick-off meeting, and various working groups were formed to, amongst others, clarify the concept on enhanced community services, and to sharpen the view on the planned collaborative work on interoperability and establishment of domain-specific languages in weather and climate models.

We thank all participants for the contributions to make our meeting a success and look forward to intense exchange and cutting-edge developments in ESIWACE2!

New Website Design

With ESIWACE2 taking off, our website has been re-designed to bundle information on both phases of ESIWACE. Find out more about the projects ESIWACE and ESIWACE2, their trainings and services at www.esiwace.eu and stay tuned for updates via our communication channels (newsletters, [Twitter](#), [Zenodo](#), etc.)!

¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/2573893#.XKXpVaSxU2w>

2nd DYAMOND-ESiWACE Hackathon

Due to the success of the first hackathon that was organised in summer 2018 by the Max-Planck Institute for Meteorology to analyse the global high-resolution simulation data from [DYAMOND](#) experiments, a second workshop and hackathon is scheduled for 18-21 June 2019 in Mainz. The event targets an even closer collaboration between international scientists involved in DYAMOND and ESiWACE. One and a half days of the event will be dedicated to a workshop with presentations on HPC and scientific findings that have been achieved through DYAMOND and ESiWACE, followed by another one and a half days of hackathon to further analyse the huge amounts of DYAMOND model data—which has just reached about 1 PB! If you are interested in the event, [please click here](#) for more information; registration deadline is 1 May 2019.

Figure 2. 10 DYAMOND high-resolution runs with different models and one satellite picture. Can you spot the differences? A larger version of the image can be downloaded at <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/dyiamond>. Courtesy by Niklas Röber, DKRZ

Snapshots

DKRZ is currently preparing the second DYAMOND-ESiWACE hackathon together with MPI-M and DWD.

ECMWF is investigating the difference of simulations for hydrostatic and non-hydrostatic equations as well as the impact of the size of the time step in more detail for simulations with up to 1km resolution.

BSC is continuing the experiments on Mare Nostrum 4 to increase the performance of the EC-Earth demonstrator (evaluating impact of the current I/O strategy).

Currently, MPI-M is performing research on the architecture and functional requirements of the interface between the climate data operators cdo and the Earth System Data Middleware ESDM.

An updated development plan for OASIS3-MCT was officially approved by the OASIS Advisory Board; this plan defines the next developments to tackle during the ESiWACE2 period.

SMHI is currently preparing major component upgrades for the next model version, which is a continuation of the EC-Earth/OpenIFS version developed in ESiWACE and will be the basis for the EC-Earth version used in ESiWACE2.

Having finalised the work in collaboration with IPSL to optimise NEMO in a 1 km target resolution via the BENCH configuration, the Center of Excellence in Performance Programming (CEPP) of Bull Atos is now working on a paper that is planned to be submitted before the end of the project. This work has been presented at the NEMO HPC Working Group meeting in April 2019.

ETH Zurich / CSCS is currently preparing for the Docker Container hackathon (autumn 2019), as well as participating in the ESIWACE2 work package 3 to benchmark ICON on Graphics Processing Units (GPUs).

The projects ESIWACE and ESIWACE2 have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreements No 675191 and 823988.